

THE HISTORY OF CATS IN JAPAN, THE ORIGIN OF “NEKO”

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Abstrakt. *This thesis is devoted to the “Neko” wild cat mentioned in Japanese literature and its pictorial expressions, the history of this animal’s appearance, and forms of use in the context of Japan. The research raised issues not mentioned before, thereby analyzing the subject area of Japanese literature.*

Keywords: *cat, Neko, animal, Japanese literature, culture*

Intraduction.

The arrival and settlement of cats and the “Neko” that appears in literature

Recent groundbreaking research has unveiled that the ancestors of the domestic cats and house cats that grace modern Japan arrived in Kyushu during the Heian period, then proliferated during the Kamakura period, and spread further north across the Japanese archipelago. This crucial information, derived by extracting and analyzing genetic information from the blood of modern cats, is a testament to the power of scientific investigation and has significantly enriched our understanding of the historical relationship between cats and Japanese culture [1-9].

Figure 1. Bone of an animal believed to be a cat from the Yayoi period around the 2nd century BC, unearthed at the Karakami ruins in Iki City, Nagasaki Prefecture, during an excavation survey conducted by Iki City in 2011.

While the bone unearthed at the Karakami ruins in Iki City, Nagasaki Prefecture, during an excavation survey conducted by Iki City in 2011 is believed to be that of a cat from the Yayoi period around the 2nd century BC, no species identification has been performed using genetic or amino acid analysis. Therefore, doubts remain whether it can be conclusively determined to be a “cat” bone.

Methods.

Although it has become clear that the genetic traces of “cats” date back to the Heian period, it seems that animals familiar to Japanese people as “Neko,” “nekoma,” or “tanuki (raccoon dog)” existed in the Japanese archipelago even earlier. Prior to genetic research, several archaeological arguments have been presented. Cat bones from the Yayoi period around the 2nd century BC were excavated from the Karakami ruins in Iki City, Nagasaki Prefecture [4, 5]. However, since the morphological

differences between cats and wildcats, especially in young animals, are minor, making it difficult to distinguish between the two, and no species identification has been performed using genetic or amino acid analysis, doubts remain as to whether the bones are those of “cats” [6]. Sueki (earthenware) with cat paw prints was discovered in the Mino Kofun (6th-7th century) in Himeji City, Hyogo Prefecture [7]. It has been reported that small animal footprints believed to be from a cat were found on a piece of sueki pottery from the late Kofun period (late 6th to early 7th century) found in a moat surrounding a burial mound near the ruins of the Koudo-ji Temple, a national historic site in Mihama-cho, Fukui Prefecture[8]. However, there are some difficulties in assuming that these bones and footprints are the direct ancestors of the domestic cats (domestic cats) living in modern Japan. The Iriomote wildcat and the Tsushima wildcat lived in the Stone Age before the establishment of Japanese civilization. They are thought to have migrated from the continent to the Japanese archipelago, connected to the mainland during the glacial period 100,000 to 200,000 years ago. The Iriomote wildcat and the Tsushima wildcat are members of the *Bengalese* genus, which branched off from the *Bengalese* cat and are genetically different from the domestic cat, which belongs to the *Felis* genus. They do not mate with each other in the natural environment [9]. DNA testing is required to distinguish them.

Figure 2. Sue ware with cat paw prints excavated from the Mino Kofun (6th to 7th century) in Himeji City, Hyogo Prefecture.

From the Asuka to the Nara period, animals resembling cats were collectively called 'raccoon dogs (Nekomata). Among them were “neko,” related to modern wildcats, and unlike today, they lived in large numbers within human habitats. It is not scientifically known whether there was a species that was related to modern housecats. Cats appeared in historical documents from the Heian period, such as “Konjaku Monogatari” (compiled after the 1120s), a significant historical document. In 'Okura no Daibu Fujiwara no Kiyokado, Neko wo Osoreru Koto' (Okura no Daibu Fujiwara no Kiyokado, Neko wo Osoreru Koto), there is a story about a man who hated cats [15]. It is assumed that “neko” were already common animals at the time of this story. However, it has yet to be confirmed that these were domestic or house cats (ieneko) living in modern Japan. The theory that cats related to modern house cats (Renko) came from the continent during the Heian or Nara period is consistent with the results of genetic analysis [2, 3]. However, it is also certain that raccoon dogs (nekomas) inhabited the Japanese archipelago and lived in cities before that.

The following description is from Sakujin Kirino and Yutaka Yoshikado's “The History of Cats in Japan” [16].

Results.

Fujiwara no Sukekimi, who appears in 'Okura no Daifu Fujiwara no Kiyotaka, Kowa Nekogo' in the “Konjaku Monogatari,” is known for collecting taxes in a truly unique way. Fujiwara no Kiyotaka tried to avoid paying the government taxes he should have paid. His weakness was well-known on the streets. He was 'afraid of cats.' People would bring out cats in front of him and tease him. Fujiwara no Sukekimi was clever. Fujiwara no Sukekimi was clever. He invented a 'cat torture' that would bring some people joy by having Kiyokaze surrounded by five cats and dogs in a small room. While seemingly humorous, this story reflects the unique relationship between cats and humans in Japanese history. Kiyokaze surrendered and delivered all the official goods at once.

“Cat-Fearing Tayu” was regularly toyed with in cat pranks. Cats were just around the city. The cats used for “cat torture” were said to be “grey-spotted” cats, “over one foot tall,” with “eyes as red as amber.” The original cat breed was an agouti, with “stripes on each hair,” a full blackish-brown color (whole-body pattern), and a wildcat type. The ‘grey spots’ were that. These “cat pranks” were playful acts and reflected the cultural perception of cats in Japanese society, particularly in the Heian period.

During the Heian period, it is possible that “cats” that would be classified as “wildcats” today lived in the city.

Descution

On the other hand, the word "Chinese cat" appears in documents from the Heian period. It is thought that the name Karaneko may have come from the Tang dynasty (618-907, China) [11, 12]. Moreover, Karaneko was a scarce animal at the time. For example, in the 34th chapter of *The Tale of Genji* (written around 1001 and completed around 1021), Wakana no Ue says, “Kaneko no Ito Chiisaku o Kashige Naru wo (Karaneko is very small and cute...)”. Until the Middle Ages, cats were precious animals, and it was expected to keep them tied to a string, as shown in *Figura 3*. As a result, there was no opportunity for them to breed, and the number of cats stayed relatively high. In the 14th century, a picture scroll called *Ishiyama-dera Engi Emaki* (*Ishiyama-dera Engi Emaki*) depicts a cat tied to a merchant's house. It is assumed that the house was wealthy enough to keep a cat. Also, as shown in *Figure 4*, a woman from the ancient period, painted by Suzuki Harunobu, an ukiyo-e artist of the Edo period, comforts a cat tied to a string.

Figure 3. “Ishiyama-dera Engi Emaki” (Produced between 1324 and 1805)
A cat on a leash in the home of a wealthy merchant.

Figure 4. Suzuki Harunobu (1725? -70), Collection of the Boston Museum of Fine Arts
Ancient woman and a cat on a leash

It is said that the number of cats began to increase during the Sengoku to Edo periods [13]. As the era progressed, the population of Kyoto increased, and rat damage became more serious. In 1602, the Kyoto Shoshidai (the shogunate's administrative agency established in Kyoto) issued the “Cats at Large” by Tokugawa Ieyasu and had cats patrol the streets to catch rats. This was recorded in the diary of Nishinotoin Tokiyoshi (1589-1639 AD). A notice prohibiting keeping cats tied up or buying and selling cats was posted at Ichijo-no-Tsuji in Kyoto and spread nationwide. This marked a significant turning point in the history of Japanese cats [14]. From then on, cats were allowed to live freely in the city. Unlike when they were tied up and kept indoors, cats were now free to breed, increasing their numbers. In the flourishing Edo culture, cats were featured in various cultural works by people of all classes, from the upper class to the ordinary people, ushering in an age of prosperity. As shown in Figure 5, many cats were depicted in ukiyo-e prints.

Figure 5. Utagawa Kuniyoshi (1798-1861) from “Sono mama Higuchi: 53 cat-keeping stories.”

Cats drawn in the Edo period are characterized by their short tails, as seen in Figure 5, and their tails are often bent in the middle. In contrast to the cats drawn before the Edo period, most of which have long, gently curving tails, one cannot help but feel something unusual about them. One theory is that the cause lies in the relationship between Chinese cats (neko) and cat demons (nekomata). Chinese cats and nekomata have an exciting relationship in Japanese folklore and yokai legends. This relationship between the two has influenced the tastes towards cats of ordinary people since the Edo period and even the distribution of cat species living in modern Japan.

Chinese cats were precious creatures from China and lived in the depths of the aristocrats' mansions and members of the imperial family, where they were adored. For this reason, their mysterious nature and unique abilities have often been spoken of. In the Kamakura period *Kokin Chomonshu* (1254, Tachibana Shigeki), there is a story about a Chinese cat kept at a mountain villa in Saga that ran away holding a treasured sword for protection, and it is said that this cat had transformed into a demon.

Nekomata, a cat-like monster, is a yokai in folklore and ghost stories from all over Japan. It is said to be an old cat that transforms into a monster (Figure 6). The oldest mention of nekomata is in *Meigetsuki* (1180–1235), a diary written by Fujiwara Teika, a nobleman of the Kamakura period. In an entry for August 2, 1233 (the first year of Tenpuku), there is a description of a “nekomata” that killed and ate several people in Nara in one night. Also, in *Tsurezuregusa* (Yoshida Kenko, 1330–1331), there is a description of a “nekomata” in Volume 226. This section introduces the story of a monster called “Nekomata” that lives deep in the mountains and eats people.

Figure 6. “Cat-mata” by Edo period artist Sawaki Takayuki (1707-72), from “Hyakkai Zukan” (Illustrated Scroll of One Hundred Monsters)

There are two main types of nekomata. One is a nekomata living in the mountains, and the other is a cat kept in a human home that grows old and transforms. The connection between karaneke and nekomata is especially seen in the latter type. As karaneke live a long life and grow old, their mystical powers increase, and they transform into nekomata. In the Edo period, the belief that a cat kept for a long time would become a nekomata as it grew older became common, and a custom of avoiding keeping cats for a long time was born. In this way, karaneke’s mysticism profoundly influences nekomata folklore, and the two are closely related to Japanese yokai culture. This even influences the distribution of cat types in modern books. In modern Japan, many cats with tails are bent in the middle, known as “tail-bending cats” or “hook-tailed cats.” [17] There are so many “tail-bending cats” in Japan due to several historical and genetic factors. During the Edo period, Dejima in Nagasaki

was a trading base with the Netherlands. Dutch trading ships brought cats with bent tails from Indonesia to exterminate rats. It is said that these cats landed in Nagasaki and bred there. The characteristic of bent-tail cats is genetic, and a gene called HES7 (Hairy and Enhancer of Split 7) is involved. HES7 is a gene that plays a vital role in forming somites. If this gene is mutated, the tail vertebrae decrease, the tail becomes shorter, the tail vertebrae are deformed, and the tail becomes bent [17] (*Figure 7*).

During the Edo period, it was believed that long-tailed cats, including Chinese cats, would split their tails into two over time and become the yōkai “nekomata,” so “bent tail cats” were favored because they would not be able to transform if their tails were bent from the beginning. In addition, bent-tail cats were said to “bring good luck” and were treasured as talismans for prosperous business. It is believed that the combination of these factors led to the widespread appearance of bent-tail cats in Japan. Many people love bent-tail cats because of their unique appearance and historical background.

Figure 7. X-ray image of the tail of a “curved cat.”

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YAPONIYADA MUSHUKLAR TARIXI: “NEKO”NING KELIB CHIQISHI

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu tezis yapon adabiyotida tilga olingan “Neko” yovvoyi mushuki va uning tasviriy ifodalari, ushbu hayvonning paydo bo‘lish tarixi va Yaponiya kontekstida foydalanish shakllariga bag‘ishlangan. Tadqiqot ilgari tilga olinmagan masalalarni ko‘tardi va shu bilan yapon adabiyotining mavzu sohasini tahlil qildi.

Kalit so‘zlar: mushuk, Neko, hayvon, yapon adabiyoti, madaniyati